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Will a new national park help preserve the isolated Aral saiga population?

On 4th March 2022, the Government of Uzbekistan issued a decree designating five new national natural parks in four regions of Uzbekistan on lands managed by the forestry department. The Aralkum National Park will be established in Muynak District of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, covering an area of about 1.0 million hectares: lex.uz/ru/docs/5892355. Aralkum is a new anthropogenic desert that has formed on the dry bottom of the Aral Sea as a result of destructive human activity. This is the youngest desert in Central Asia, otherwise called the White Desert after the colour of sea salt crystallised on the former seabed. Despite the young age of the desert, which continues to grow in size through ongoing shrinkage of the remaining body of water, and the

instability of the new territory, which is just beginning to be populated by terrestrial plants and animals replacing marine organisms, some areas of the Aralkum boast rich biodiversity with diverse and unique flora and fauna that have formed over a long historical period. In particular, the new protected area will include an archipelago of former islands (Vozrozhdeniye, Konstantin, Lazarev, Bellingshausen and some other), adjacent territories of the Western and Central Aral Sea (coastline and the remaining body of water) and the dry bottom. The northern boundary of the Aralkum protected area coincides with the state border with the Republic of Kazakhstan.

The vegetation of the national park is characterized by the monodominance

of landscape species (*Artemisia terrae-albae*, *Haloxylon ammodendron*, *Salsola orientalis*). The isolation of the area has allowed this vegetation to retain its structure, in the absence of human disturbance and grazing. At the same time, the sands of Aralkum are a natural laboratory for observing the natural course of vegetation change. Currently, it clearly reflects three stages of succession: psammoseries (psammophilous succession), haloseries (halophytic succession) and potamoseries (tugai vegetation succession). The vegetation that forms during each of these stages is original and has no analogues. Currently, 123 species of higher vascular plants belonging to 90 genera and 31 families have been recorded in the areas which used to be islands. *Artemisia terrae-albae*, *Salsola orientalis* and *Haloxylon ammodendron* communities, which are typical of sandy and gypsum deserts in Uzbekistan, have remained only on Vozrozhdeniye Island. The island also features rare species such as *Astragalus brachypus* (the first record in Uzbekistan), *Linaria dolichoceras*, *Chondrilla ambigua* and *Astragalus lehmannianus* (the previous record was a herbarium specimen collected in 1921).

Typical sandy landscape of Vozrozhdeniye Island.
Photo by Alexander Esipov

Endangered caracal was recorded by camera trap.
Photo by Alexander Esipov

These Upper Cretaceous geological concretions are found on Vozrozhdeniye Island.

Photo by Elena Bykova

Huge flocks of flamingos can be seen quite often in the western Aral. Photo by Elena Bykova

The vertebrate fauna of Aralkum currently comprises 128 species, including 1 amphibian, 12 reptiles, 93 birds and 22 mammals. Having developed in strict isolation, it has unique relict features. Historically, the vertebrate fauna of the former islands of the Aral Sea is most closely related to the fauna of the surrounding deserts – the Ustyurt plateau and the Kyzylkum desert, while structurally it is the most similar to the Ustyurt fauna. Recently, as the Aral Sea has shrunk and the islands have connected with the mainland to form a new topography, it has begun to change. The result is the development of new faunal complexes, which have no analogues elsewhere in the world.

The national park will be a home for rare species such as the Russian tortoise *Testudo horsfieldii*, Tatar sand boa *Eryx tataricus*, blotched rat snake *Elaphe sauromates*, greater flamingo *Phoenicopterus roseus*, osprey *Pandion haliaetus*, golden eagle *Aquila chrysaetos*, lesser kestrel *Falco naumanni*, pintailed sandgrouse *Pterocles alchata*, Brandt's hedgehog *Paraechinus hypomelas*, corsac fox *Vulpes corsac*, caracal *Caracal caracal*, and saiga *Saiga tatarica*.

The saiga antelope is one of the key species in the Aralkum desert, which currently inhabits small islands, the shore of the remaining West Aral Sea and the dry bottom in the south-east. The saiga population is resident, numbering about 100. In the late 19th century, these ungulates were abundant on Vozrozhdeniye Island. L. S. Berg (1908) reports that in the spring of 1897 an industrialist killed 1,500 saigas to sell their horns to China. In 2007–2010, at least 100–150 saiga individuals lived in the Aralkum, both on the original islands and on the former bottom of the Aral Sea now covered with vegetation (Nurijanov, 2010). Human activity has intensified in recent years in connection with projects to afforest the drained bottom and the extraction of hydrocarbons, so saigas now prefer to stay in places most inaccessible to humans. In addition to poaching, which in the past significantly reduced saiga numbers on the former islands and adjacent territory, the other negative impact is from the industrial sector developing in the region. Intensive infrastructure construction at the new West Aral natural gas field began in 2022, by the company Sanoat Energetika Guruhi. The activities include the development of

ultra-deep drilling wells (up to 4,000 m) and the construction of quarries and gravel roads. Heavy vehicles move almost around the clock on the previously virgin territory of the islands and the dry bottom, which has an extremely negative impact on saigas and other fauna.

Saigas, as well as other inhabitants of the former islands (wild boars, hares), are also illegally hunted. Hunting is limited because the territory is controlled by border forces, but both gas industry workers and local residents visiting the territory to gather metal waste remaining on the site of a former military base are reliably known to be involved in illegal hunting and do not miss the opportunity to poach wild animals. The military base is known as Kantubek military town or Aralsk-7. It was located on the Vozrozhdeniye Island from 1942 to 1992, and was completely demolished in 2019. Because it was militarised and therefore off-limits, Vozrozhdeniye historically experienced very low human pressure. However, along with other uninhabited islands it has recently, over a very short period, faced a wide range of threats, including poaching, habitat disturbance and degradation. There is also a recently erected fence along the

Kazakh-Uzbek border, which is a grave obstruction to large and medium-size animals (see SN-15, 21).

Currently, a programme entitled “Vozrozhdeniye Island” is underway, supported by the UK Government’s Darwin Initiative, the Whitley Fund for Nature and People’s Trust for Endangered Species. The programme is working to zone the territory of the national park, which, in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, will include core, recreational and economic development zones. Proper zoning will help balance biodiversity conservation goals and the socio-economic

development of the territory, as well as enabling industrial companies to fulfil their obligations to prevent and mitigate their negative impacts on biodiversity. This will help to ensure the integrity and sustainability of the fragile ecosystems of the Aral Sea.

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Very clear and extremely salty water of the Aral Sea. Photo by Alexander Esipov